

o-Vanillin and its Semicarbazone Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II) and Palladium(II)

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The chelating properties of Schiff bases derived from *o*-hydroxyaldehydes and ketones display manifold applications in medicine, industry and agriculture¹. The complexing behaviour of Schiff bases² and their biological activities³ have been reported. One such aldehyde is *o*-vanillin and its Schiff base formation has been described earlier^{4,5}. The present paper reports the ligational behaviour of *o*-vanillin and *o*-vanillin semicarbazone with cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II) and palladium(II).

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complexes (Table 1) reveal that the complexes formed with *o*-vanillin (HL) have 1 : 2 stoichiometry whereas it is 1 : 1 in case of *o*-vanillin semicarbazone (H₂L') complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II}. The presence of lattice and coordinated water in the complexes is confirmed by ir and thermogravimetry and formulated in Table 1. All chelates are insoluble in most solvents except DMSO and DMF. Their solutions are nonelectrolytes as inferred from their low conductance values.

Ir spectra : Ir spectral data are presented in Table 2. The spectrum of H₂L' shows specific ir bands for azomethine linkage (C=N stretch) at 1570 cm⁻¹ and N-N stretch at 970-940 cm⁻¹, diagnostic of Schiff base formation⁶, which shifts to higher frequency on coordination. New bands are observed at 1560-1530 cm⁻¹ characteristic

of ν_{C-N=N=C} and at 375-460 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{M-N}, thus confirming that azomethine nitrogen actively takes part in coordination. Absence of ν_{NH} bands in the complexes too confirm the Schiff base formation and its enolisation in complexes⁷. In case of H₂L' complexes, bands due to ketonic ν_{C=O} at 1660 cm⁻¹ in the ligand is absent and new bands characteristic of (NCO⁻) appear in 1380-1400 cm⁻¹ region presumably due to the amide ⇌ imidol tautomerism of the ligand and its subsequent coordination through imidol oxygen⁸.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND CONDUCTANCE DATA OF *o*-VANILLIN (HL), *o*-VANILLIN SEMICARBAZONE (H₂L') AND THEIR COMPLEXES

Compd./ (Colour)	Analysis% : Found/Calcd.)				Λ _m [*] Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹ in DMF
	Metal	C	H	N	
HL (Green)	-	63.1 (63.2)	5.2 (5.7)	-	-
[CoL ₂].H ₂ O (Yellow)	15.3 (15.6)	50.3 (50.7)	4.3 (4.2)	-	7.9
[NiL ₂].2H ₂ O (Green)	15.3 (14.9)	47.9 (48.4)	4.7 (4.5)	-	5.5
[CuL ₂] (Yellow)	17.8 (17.6)	52.3 (52.7)	3.8 (3.8)	-	6.3
[ZnL ₂].2H ₂ O (Yellow)	17.1 (17.7)	47.3 (47.6)	4.4 (4.5)	-	5.1
H ₂ L' (White)	-	52.1 (51.7)	5.5 (5.3)	20.1 (20.1)	-
[CoL'.H ₂ O] (Brown)	20.0 (20.7)	38.3 (38.0)	3.4 (3.8)	6.0 (6.3)	10.9
[NiL'.H ₂ O] (Green)	22.0 (22.1)	38.0 (38.1)	3.8 (3.9)	6.1 (6.4)	13.2
[CuL'.H ₂ O] (Green)	22.9 (22.2)	39.9 (39.8)	3.3 (3.7)	6.0 (6.2)	8.5
[PdL'.H ₂ O] (Black)	35.6 (33.8)	31.7 (29.4)	2.6 (3.0)	10.9 (11.4)	12.2

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TABLE 2—IR SPECTRAL DATA* (cm^{-1}) OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{OH}	ν_{OH} water	ν_{OH} aldehyde	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	ν_{OCH_3}	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$
<i>oV</i>	3 400	—	2 940	1 690	2 840	—	1 210	—	—	—
$[\text{CoL}_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	3 430	2 930	1 640	2 840	—	1 250	—	510	—
$[\text{NiL}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	3 500	2 940	1 650	2 830	—	1 250	—	505	—
$[\text{CuL}_2]$	—	—	2 922	1 640	2 830	—	1 240	—	510	—
$[\text{ZnL}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	—	3 440	2 912	1 660	2 830	—	1 235	—	500	—
$\text{H}_2\text{L}'$	3 430	—	—	1 660	2 825	1 570	1 270	—	—	—
$[\text{CoL}' \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	—	3 420	—	—	2 840	1 575	1 280	1 625	520	400
$[\text{NiL}' \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	—	3 440	—	—	2 850	1 580	1 290	1 628	515	455
$[\text{CuL}' \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	—	3 460	—	—	2 845	1 585	1 285	1 610	530	375
$[\text{PdL}' \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	—	3 510	—	—	2 860	1 600	1 295	1 630	520	460

*In CsI.

Presence of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ gives evidential support to the above conclusions. In ir spectra of the complexes, a sharp band at $1\ 690\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ of free aldehyde group in HL shifts noticeably in the metal complexes to lower frequency by $10\text{--}60\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ indicating the involvement of carbonyl oxygen of CHO group in coordination to metal ions⁹.

A distinct band present at $\sim 3\ 400\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in both the ligands disappears in spectra of the complex which indicates coordination of the deprotonated OH of the phenolic hydroxyl group. This is further supported by an upward shift of phenolic $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ at $1\ 210\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ by $10\text{--}40\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and the presence of $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ band in the complexes¹⁰.

In all the HL complexes (except Cu^{II} complex) a broad band is observed at $3\ 500\text{--}3\ 400\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ region¹¹ assignable to ν_{OH} of lattice water. Absence of $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\gamma_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ peculiar for coordinated water, confirms the presence of lattice water. Whereas in $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$ complexes additional bands are found around $1\ 630\text{--}1\ 600$ and $850\text{--}840\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ assignable to deformation and rocking modes of coordinated water respectively¹².

Magnetic moment and electronic spectral data : The electronic spectrum of HL in DMF shows a band at $\sim 268\ \text{nm}$ due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ CT transition of the benzene ring and another at $330\ \text{nm}$ due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the

carbonyl group¹³, whereas in $\text{H}_2\text{L}'$ a broad band is observed at $\sim 350\ \text{nm}$ involving delocalisation throughout the azomethine chromosphere¹⁴. In case of the complexes these bands shift to higher wavelength supporting the evidence of their coordination sites. In Co-oV complex (in DMF) three transitions arising from ground state $^4A_{2g}$ to higher excited state are noticed corresponding to the tetrahedral geometry at $490, 390$ and $270\ \text{nm}$ respectively, whereas in Co-oVSC complex two bands are observed (Table 3). In Co-oV complex the magnetic moment value is found to be $4.4\ \text{B.M.}$ whereas in Co-oVSC this value is $2.99\ \text{B.M.}$ lying within the respective range for tetrahedral and square-planar geometry. In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes (recorded in DMF) the ν_2 and ν_3 bands are observed at 430 and $620\ \text{nm}$ in Ni-oV and at 570 and $800\ \text{nm}$ in the Ni-oVSC complex respectively. The Ni-oV complex shows magnetic moment of $4.0\ \text{B.M.}$ and Ni-oVSC of $2.9\ \text{B.M.}$ corresponding to tetrahedral and distorted tetrahedral geometries respectively. The $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-oV}$ complex shows two bands at 680 and $470\ \text{nm}$ assigned to the two transitions $^2E_g \leftarrow ^2B_{1g}$ and $^2A_{1g} \leftarrow ^2B_{1g}$ respectively, whereas the complex formed with oVSC shows a very broad band at $620\ \text{nm}$ owing to a single first transition allowed for the $d^9\ \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ ion in the complex indicating a square-planar geometry. The magnetic moment values of 1.8 and $2.2\ \text{B.M.}$ confirm the square-planar geometry for both the complexes¹⁵.

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC MOMENT AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Medium	λ_{\max} (nm)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
HL	DMF	268 330	—
[CoL ₂].H ₂ O	DMF	490 390	4.4
[NiL ₂].2H ₂ O	DMF	270 620 430 380	4.0
[CuL ₂]	MgO	680 470	1.8
H ₂ L'	DMF	350	—
[CoL'.H ₂ O]	DMF	800 400	3.0
[NiL'.H ₂ O]	DMF	800 570	2.9
[CuL'.H ₂ O]	MgO	620 465	2.2
[PdL'.H ₂ O]	DMF	320	Diamag.

¹H nmr spectra : The ¹H nmr spectrum of the parent ligand *o*V recorded in DMSO-d₆ displayed only one sharp singlet at δ 10.28 but in the solvent CDCl₃ two distinct signals were observed at δ 11.04 and 9.86 due to OH and CHO groups respectively. Multiplets are observed at δ 7.13, 7.07 and 6.92 due to the aromatic protons and a sharp singlet at δ 3.86 is due to the presence of methoxy group at C(3). From the comparison of the nmr spectral data of the coordinated and free *o*V only CHO and OH groups are affected. On complexation with Zn^{II} the phenolic signal at δ 11.04 disappears, indicating its deprotonation to coordinate with this metal ion. The proton signal for the aldehyde group observed at δ 9.86 as a singlet in the ligand is shifted downfield in the spectra of *o*V complexes. This is due to deshielding caused by the donation of lone-pair of electrons by the carbonyl oxygen to the central metal ion, resulting in the formation of coordinate bond¹⁶. The lowfield position of H(6) relative to those of H(5) and H(4) could be attributed to the electron-withdrawing nature of the aldehyde group present on C(1). The ¹H nmr spectral data of HL (DMSO-d₆ and CDCl₃) and its Zn^{II} complex (in DMSO-d₆) are presented in Table 4.

TABLE 4—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA (δ ppm) OF *o*-VANILLIN (HL) AND [ZnL₂].2H₂O

<i>o</i> -Vanillin (HL) in CDCl ₃	<i>o</i> -Vanillin (HL) in DMSO-d ₆	[ZnL ₂].2H ₂ O in DMSO-d ₆	Assignment
7.06(m)	7.26(s)	7.37(s)	H(6)
6.92(t)	6.88(t)	6.07(s)	H(5)
7.13(t)	7.23(s)	8.31(s)	H(4)
3.87(s)	3.85(s)	3.50(s)	OCH ₃
11.04(s)	—	—	OH
9.86(s)	10.28(s)	10.19(s)	CHO

It can be concluded from the results that HL acts as bidentate monobasic ligand coordinating via carbonyl oxygen and deprotonised phenolic hydroxyl group, whereas H₂L' acts as a tridentate dibasic ligand coordinating through azomethine nitrogen, enolic oxygen and phenolic oxygen. The representative structures (Fig. 1) show that all the HL complexes are formed in 1 : 2 stoichiometry.

Fig. 1.

Experimental

The physicochemical techniques and all the chemicals used were the same as already described^{4,5}. The synthesis of the ligand *o*-vanillin semicarbazone (H_2L') was also reported earlier.

Metal complexes with o-vanillin : A mixture of the ligand and the metal acetates (2 : 1 molar ratio) was refluxed for 2–3 h on a water-bath. To an aqueous metal salt solution (0.005 M) containing $Co(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1.24 g), $Ni(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1.24 g), $Cu(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot H_2O$ (1.00 g) or $Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ (1.10 g) was added an ethanolic solution (0.005 M) of *o*-vanillin (1.52 g) gradually. The complexes thus obtained were filtered, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried over anhydrous $CaCl_2$.

Metal complexes with o-vanillin semicarbazone : A 1 : 1 mixture of *o*-vanillin semicarbazone (0.005 mol, 1.05 g) in hot DMF-ethanol solvent mixture and aqueous metal salt solution (0.005 M) was refluxed on a heating mantle for 4–5 h. The solid complex was separated on cooling which was filtered and isolated as above [in case of palladium complex, K_2PdCl_4 was prepared by mixing KCl (2 mmol) and $PdCl_2$ (1 mmol) in aqueous medium on a water-bath]. All the complexes were found to be air-stable and insoluble in common organic solvents (ethanol, chloroform, acetone, benzene, methanol, dioxan) except DMF and DMSO.

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